

The Citationless h-index: Concerning a Heuristic Point of View Toward Hirsch’s Index

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Abstract

In this conference contribution we present a preliminary heuristic approach towards estimating a scholar’s h-index even when her citation record is incomplete. A citation-less h-index may sound as a contradiction in terms, but given the mathematical methodologies of bibliometrics and citation analyse in particular, the quantitative entities usually employed are governed by formal relations that in principle makes it possible to calculate an h-index based on assumptions related to the statistical citation patterns in a given field of research.

Keywords: Citation analysis, Research metrics, Bibliometrics

1. Introduction

In 2005 J. E. Hirsch proposed an index, defined as the number of papers h with citations greater than or equal to h as being “a useful index to characterize the scientific output of a researcher” (cf. Hirsch 2005). By sorting and ordering citations according to a decreasing number of citations to actual papers in an author’s record (the paper’s rank), the citation record can be translated into a “Hirsch list” of papers ranked according to decreasing number of citations per paper.

While Hirsch’s h-index is a metric widely used, it is also criticized for being a measure made and used only by amateurs, for being a metric without any substantial evidence supporting its value, and in general for being a number that we do not know what measures (e.g. Brito & Navarro 2021). On top of that, the data used for its calculation are incomplete and increasingly

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being inflated: The average number of authors per article has been constantly increasing over the last century (cf. Fanelli & Larivière 2016) and so-called citation cartels are being established to boost both individual citation rates and journal impact factors (cf. Kojaku et al. 2021).

What adds to the critique of the h-index is the fact that it cannot be used for comparison across disciplines (Brito & Navarro 2021). Firstly, citation culture differs across disciplines (cf. Miranda & Garcia-Carpintero 2019). Put boldly, the chance of a Social Science and Humanities (SSH) publication having one or more citations after a given number of years is significantly smaller than a Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) publication. Secondly, publication patterns differ across disciplines: Broadly speaking, SSH publishes more books and with fewer authors per publication, while STEM produces more articles with many authors (cf. Henriksen 2018). And while STEM almost only publishes in English, SSH researchers are more likely to have non-English language publications, for which the potential citing clientele is much smaller (cf. Kulczycki et al. 2020). Nevertheless comparison happens all the time.

On top of this the h-index cannot be used to compare researchers with different levels of academic experience since it does not take the researcher's age into consideration: It takes time for a researcher to write publications and to get cited, therefore a relatively unsuccessful senior researcher may have a higher h-index than a very successful junior researcher (cf. Kelly & Jennions 2007).

Finally, the calculation of a 'true' h-index assumes that a complete list of publications and their citations can be obtained for any researcher. But as pointed out by Mongon & Paul-Hus no scientific database has full coverage (cf. Mongeon & Paul-Hus 2016).

Consequently, we agree with Brito & Navarro that "... the use of the h-index in research evaluations ... should disappear" (cf. Brito & Navarro 2021). However, given its success, we find it hard to believe that it will. Therefore, we examine the possibility of developing a method where the h-index can be normalized according to disciplines.

The rationale for our paper is threefold: Recently, and in a different context we conducted text-mining of academic job ads and found a steep increase in the number of times the employers' expectations to the candidates h-index is occurring. And only recently at our university's annual celebration in 2021 an honorary doctor was promoted with the words "He has an h-index over 90" implying that this was an h-index above what could be expected within this particular professor's discipline. But what is a good h-index in

any particular discipline for a researcher of any given age? The world record h-index of 300 is held by Ronald C. Kessler, from Harvard University. His discipline is health care policy. An h-index of 90 does not even make it into the top 5,000 of (google-based) researcher h-indexes. Our point is, that the h-index is used in an arbitrary manner. Since we believe that this will continue to be used so, we set out to limit the randomness by establishing a standard for the various disciplines against which one may ascertain what a good h-index is in each discipline.

Secondly, we have (re-)experienced an increased focus on cross-disciplinary research over the last decades (cf. Sonetti et al. 2020). We applaud this. However, it also means that SSH researchers are increasingly competing directly with STEM researchers for jobs and funds and in our professional life at the university library we are all there constantly being asked to calculate h-indexes for researchers, for university management or for research support units who use h-index for researcher assessments related to recruitment, promotion, obtaining of funding and so on. In other words, the renaissance of the cross-disciplinary research emphasizes the necessity of establishing a standard for predicting a reasonable value of an h-index within the various disciplines.

And finally, currently every scientist has as many h-indexes as there are databases that index both publications and citations (cf. Hu et al. 2020). The h-indexes we normally calculate are Google Scholar, Scopus, Web of Science h-indexes, which differs significantly as can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1: h-indexes of the authors at time of publication in three widely used publication databases (accessed during April 2021).

Authors	Scopus	WoS	Google Scholar
Bertil F. Dorch	13	13	16
Daniella B. Deutz	7	7	8
Charlotte N. Wien	6	18	10

There appears to be no consensus among researchers on which one to use for obvious reasons. The need for a shared standard is evident.

Therefore, the aim of this paper is to create a model that enables us to predict the h-index of a researcher from any given discipline based only on publication data.

The reason why we focus on publication data alone is that we assume that it is in the individual researcher’s interest and capability to ensure and

to maintain a full and complete list of publications, while keeping track of citations is much more difficult.

2. Modelling the h-index

It takes time for most papers to accumulate citations. Empirically, if an author continues to be active and publish new papers on a regular basis, we know that her publication record will generally display more papers with fewer or no citations, and less papers with more or a lot of citations.

To follow the line of arguments above, we model the h-index by considering the publication record of a highly cited author with many publications, at any given time, as reflected by a Hirsch list that is a hyperbolic function shifted toward a high number of citations for a few papers, declining passed h citations, to very low number of citations far beyond publication number h . The mathematical details of this approach will be published in a forthcoming paper.

In a log-normal diagram, the distribution is then nearly linear for intermediate paper ranks corresponding to the expected range of the h-index.

Hence, the citations to each ranked document $c(p)$, are proportional to the inverse of the document's rank, p . Integration results in the total number of citations, N_c , which by using Hirsch's parameter a can be formulated as,

$$h = \sqrt{(b/a) \cdot \log N_p + C_1/a}. \quad (1)$$

The fitting factor b in this case is then the average number of citations to a researcher's top ranked publication in that discipline, while the constant C_1 should account for any citations received over the expected distribution.

Here a can be attributed as the researcher's "efficiency" in terms of attaining a high h-index, given his or her total number of citations (e.g. Deutz et al. 2020).

While by definition $a \geq 1$, already Hirsch himself finds that empirically $3 \leq a \leq 5$ in the case of the field of physics. We find similar situation in clinical research.

Having now established that the h-index depends upon the total number of publications, one can ask what is then the h-index that a researcher in any given field of research can be expected to have, given a certain number of publications N_p ?

Assuming that within each discipline there is an expected lifetime number of citations each publication can expect to attract, d (where d is basically just the disciplinary average number of citations per publication), then the total number of citations of a particular researcher in that discipline can be approximated $N_c = d \cdot N_p$ resulting in:

$$h = \sqrt{(d/a) \cdot N_p}. \quad (2)$$

In other words, knowing the disciplinary average number of citation per publication and the Hirsch's a we can in principle calculate the h-index from an individual's number of publications — assuming that this individual is approximated by the average of her discipline.

3. Method

Having presented how we model an h-index based only on the publications we will now test our model against empirical data.

To validate the proposed approach for predicting the h-index of a researcher in a given field we require the publication data of researchers in a well-defined discipline. We based this part of our study on researchers at our own institution, the University of Southern Denmark (SDU), as we have access to high quality researcher lists for each department and faculty through our institutional Current Research Information System (PURE). The publication data of each researcher can then be extracted from Scopus, the commercial publication database from Elsevier via their confirmed Scopus author ID. We chose to extract data from the following departments:

1. Physics, Chemistry and Pharmacy
2. Clinical Research
3. Business and Economics
4. Mathematics and Computer Science.

We assume that the disciplines corresponding to these departments can be considered to be well-defined as represented in Scopus, while we note that the publication data of the researchers is dependent on the Scopus coverage of their field, and that especially in the Social Sciences and Humanities fields (c) a non-negligible percentage of their publications will be missing from the analysis. For each researcher we extracted the h-index h , the total number of citations N_c , and the total number of publications, N_p .

We approach the problem from two angles using data extracted from Scopus in October 2020, using the Optimization Tool in MATLAB R2020b for qualitative fitting.

- Four researchers were chosen at random (one from each of the departments), Their h-index graphs (the document rank, p , and citations to each ranked document, c) were extracted and the fitting factor, b , was qualitatively fitted.
- The publication data (N_p , N_c , h) of all researchers at each of the four departments is used. The efficiency factor, a , and the disciplinary citation rate, d , were qualitatively fitted. To validate d , we used the subject area specific citations per publication from the SciVal analysis tool, for a period of 2010–2019 and limited to publications with an affiliation including Denmark, where the subject areas are classified according to the All Science Journal Classification (ASJC) used in Scopus.

Table 2: The actual h-index of the researchers examined in Fig. 1 compared to the prediction from Eq. 1. To make the prediction the fitting factor, b is qualitatively fitted to the publication data and the coefficient $C1$ is set to 0. The $C1$ required to fit the prediction to the actual h-index is presented in the final column.

Researcher's Department	Actual h-index	Predicted h-index	C1
Physics, Chemistry and Pharmacy	40	28,3374	3514
Clinical Research	76	49,0788	17640
Business and Economics	7	6,9596	2,841
Maths and Computer Science	16	14,5826	156,5

4. Results

The h-index graphs of researchers in four different departments at the University of Southern Denmark (SDU) are shown in Fig. 1 where the citations to each ranked document, c , are presented as a function of the document rank, p , of each of their publications. Overall, the logarithmic approach to modeling the h-index curve does not closely match the researcher's publication data. Still, the model can be used to predict each researcher's h-index (Table 2). The predicted h-indices only come close to approaching the actual h-index when the absolute value of the h-index is low. Once the h-index

goes up, the model becomes overly dependent on C_1 , which here is the citation under-count of the model. For the researcher in Clinical Research C_1 is four orders of magnitude larger than for the researcher in Business and Economics, even though there is only one order of magnitude difference in the h-index.

Figure 1: The h-index graphs of researchers in four different research departments at the University of Southern Denmark (SDU) where the citations to each ranked document, c , are presented as a function of paper rank, p , of each of their publications. (a) Researcher from the Department of Physics, Chemistry and Pharmacy. (b) Researcher from the Department of Clinical Research. (c) Researcher from the Department of Business and Economics. (d) Researcher from the Department of Mathematics and Computer Science. Each point represents a single publication. The dashed lines follow the formula presented in Eq. ??, where the fitting factor b is qualitatively fitted. We note that the x-axis is in a logarithmic scale.

While this approach does enable one to make a prediction of a researcher's h-index given their N_p , it is a rather complicated way of looking at the problem: The approach requires that three factors must be estimated based on the researcher's field (a , b , and C_1) should one want to make a prediction

without basing it on any researcher in particular. The efficiency factor, a , is relatively easy to estimate based on the field of the researcher, (Hirsch 2005) and (Deutz et al. 2020).

The b fitting factor, which here is equal to the number of citations to a researcher’s top ranked publication, is another matter. Firstly, the b of a researcher typically does not affect the h-index, so it is an odd factor to include in its estimation. Secondly, while there are fields that are well and less well cited (for examples see Table 3 and Fig. 4), there does not appear to be any clear and established pattern in the number of citations a researcher’s best cited publication receives. Some publications just get lucky, due to any number of reasons ranging from social media attention, presenting a useful method, being a politically favorable topic, having a catchy title, including many international co-authors or the journal editor and so on (Yi et al. 2009; Deutz et al. 2020; Cook & Bordage 2016; Van Noorden et al. 2014).

Furthermore, while the citation under-count of the model, C_1 , does depend on the N_p of the researcher to some degree, it is unclear how many other factors influence it. It is likely that the researcher age, τ_{RA} , (i.e. the length of time since the researcher’s first publication) would affect C_1 since a publication’s number of citations can only go up over time. The disciplinary citation rate, d will likely also affect C_1 since the total number of citations a researcher has received, N_c , itself is dependent on C_1 (Eq. ??).

And there could be other less easily quantifiable factors influencing a researcher’s number of citations that may not be overlooked, such as: the strength of their academic network, the citation rate of their country, the percentage of their publications that get in to the top journals in their field, and so on (Baccini et al. 2019; Gao et al. 2020; Starbuck 2005). We can then infer that C_1 should at the least be a function of: N_p , τ_{RA} , and d , and we note that this list is non-exhaustive. While an interesting thought experiment, this approach does not bring one much closer to being able to predict a researcher’s h-index based primarily on their N_p .

5. Discussion

Consider the question “What is the h-index a researcher in any given field of research can be expected to have, given a certain number of publications N_p ?”. The h-index, h , of researchers in four different departments at the University of Southern Denmark (SDU) are shown in Fig. 2 as a function of their number of citations, N_c . Exactly half of the researchers have an

Table 3: The citation rate per publication in SciVal in relevant subject areas, from 2010–2019, limited to Danish publications. The citations per publication from 2010–2019 is used as a proxy for the disciplinary citation rate, d .

Subject classification	Citations per publication (2010 - 2019)
ASJC Business, Management and Accounting	15.2
ASJC Chemistry	24.7
ASJC Computer Science	11.0
ASJC Economics, Econometrics and Finance	12.3
ASJC Mathematics	10.3
ASJC Medicine	24.8
ASJC Pharmacology, Toxicology and Pharmaceutics	21.6
ASJC Physics and Astronomy	23.1

efficiency factor, a , as calculated from $a = N_c/h^2$, between $3 < a \leq 5$, with an average a of 4.8 ± 3.9 and an average h of 13 ± 14 .

We note that the researcher lists include many early career researchers, skewing the h of the departments down and the a up. The best fit for a varies between the different fields (Fig. ??) yet remains squarely in the range of $3 < a \leq 5$ proposed by Hirsch as the a of the ‘average physics researcher’ (Hirsch 2005).

To validate our proposed formula for estimating whether a researcher’s h-index is the norm in their respective field (Eq. 2), the h of researchers in the same four departments at the University of Southern Denmark (SDU) is presented in Fig. 3 as a function of their number of publications, N_{rmp} . For each department, the d factor has been qualitatively fitted to the data. In this approach, one could state that all researchers with an h-index above the model curve would have an above average h for their field, while those below the curve would have an h below average for their field. The determining factor here is of course d . The qualitatively fitted d ’s appear to be in close agreement with the disciplinary citation rates of each of the examined fields (Table 3). This would imply that one could use the disciplinary citation rate as a proxy for the d factor to predict what the average h-index for a researcher in that field would be from Eq. 2.

An exception is the Department of Clinical Research, presented in Fig. 3b. There are over 700 researchers in this department, and it is clear that the model does not account for the wide disparity in their achieved h-indices. The reason for this spread in h-indices is the following: within the field of Medicine the disciplinary citation rates vary wildly (Fig. 4), with publications in sub-fields like Oncology and Cardiology receiving 2 to 3 times the citations

Figure 2: The h-index, h , of researchers in four different research departments at the University of Southern Denmark (SDU) as a function of their Number of citations, N_C . (a) Department of Physics, Chemistry and Pharmacy. (b) Department of Clinical Research. (c) Department of Business and Economics. (d) Department of Mathematics and Computer Science. Each point represents the publication data of a single researcher. The dashed lines follow the formula presented in Eq. ??, where the efficiency factor, a , has been qualitatively fitted.

of those in Emergency Medicine and Family Practice. Thus, to use our model to predict the h-index of a researcher in the Department of Clinical Research, it must be broken down along sub-field lines so that the sub-field citation rates can be used in lieu of the overall disciplinary citation rate.

6. Conclusions

In this conference contribution we began by mentioning that a honorary doctor with “... an h-index over 90” has recently been promoted at our university. In our conclusion we will demonstrate whether this h-index within the given discipline is beyond what could normally be expected.

The heuristic approach presented here is based on general assumptions

Figure 3: The h-index, h , of researchers in four different research departments at the University of Southern Denmark (SDU) as a function of their Number of publications, N_p . (a) Department of Physics, Chemistry and Pharmacy. (b) Department of Clinical Research. (c) Department of Business and Economics. (d) Department of Mathematics and Computer Science. Each point represents the publication data of a single researcher. The dashed lines follow the formula presented in Eq. 2, where both the efficiency factor, a , and the disciplinary citation rate, d , have been qualitatively fitted.

about scholarly communication practices reflected e.g. in the distribution of citations, which in turn corresponds to a particular h-index.

By different methods we have firmly established that the h-index depends upon the total number of publications. This begs the question whether one can estimate the expected h-index that a researcher in any given field of research, given her total number of publications.

It turns out that the h-index is related to the square root of the total number of publications multiplied by some factor, which depends on the display of an average disciplinary practice. In other words, if a disciplinary sample are known and our method applies, it is possible to calculate the h-index for said researcher: Thus, one can estimate the h-index is for an author with a known number of publications, but an unknown h-index.

Figure 4: The citations per publication for Danish publications in SciVal, from 2010–2019 for sub-fields of the ASJC subject category of Medicine. Data extracted in Oct. 2020.

Additionally, the h-index only increase slowly as the number of publications increase, meaning that increasing publication frequency is ineffective for increasing the h-index.

We test the heuristic approach against concrete sample data supporting the general findings. However, a natural note of caution is that while it may statistically be possible to arrive at an expected h-index giving a disciplinary sample, an individual cannot and should not in general be represented by simple linear quantitative relationship: The assessment of an individual’s academical career and perceived impact is a complex ethical, social and philosophical matter transcending far beyond low dimensional quantitative modelling in the same way that the a single college grade cannot predict the lifetime achievement or societal impact of any individual.

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